

NATIONAL CENSUS POLICY: A BENCHMARK FOR PEACE, SECURITY AND DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Census exercise is designed upon the conviction that clear-cut population data, lies in its heart the roadmap that enables good planning, precise execution and defined sustainable development of any nation. Having not been able to fulfill these purposes, most of the past studies on census in Nigeria have been dedicated to prospects, challenges, housing units and politics behind the falsification of census figures. Shockingly, none have really espoused how census could be imperative for trivet of peace, security and development of the nation. However, as a point of divergent departure from the recurrent focus on census and contentious debate enveloping the population of the nation, the paper examines the indices census has on the peace, security and development of the country. The cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study using the proportionate stratified sampling techniques in the selection of 270 respondents that cut across three towns: Ado, Ikere and Ikole representing each senatorial district of Ekiti State. A structured questionnaire served as the instrument for data collection. Content analysis was used for the qualitative data. Findings revealed that there are mixed perceptions about the functionality of census cum panacea for tackling security challenges and planning for development in the country. The study recommends strict adherence to the standard decennial census exercise to ensure enhanced peace, security and development of the nation.

Keywords: National Census, Policy, Benchmark, Peace, Security, Development

Introduction

The rationale behind the idea of conducting census at regular intervals in most societies is to guarantee better performance in terms of planning sustainable development not restricted to the socio-economic sector only, but at the same time extended to other sectors for attainment of holistic development at a faster pace. Ashkpour (2019:15) observed that “censuses contain a wealth of

information about nations and societies. They structurally capture societal information needs at given times in the past. Throughout history, the censuses have served to provide information to governments, i.e. to understand the development of the nation and its population on several fronts, for decision-making purposes". In United States, for instance, Reamer (2018) noted that topical research indicates census-obtained data were used to allocate more than \$850 billion to states and localities through 302 programs in Fiscal Year 2016 alone. As such, a national census policy presents basic information on a country's population that enables seamless government planning and policy implementation that underscores all-around national development.

This importance informed the Nigerian government to specially create the Nigeria Population Commission (NPC) in 1988, domiciled under the Federal Ministry of Interior with the statutory powers to collect, analyze and disseminate demographic data in the country. Its other duties include undertaking demographic sample surveys, compile, collate and publish migration and civil registration statistics and also to monitor the country's population policy (www.devex.com). Therefore, it is deducible that the Commission superintends everything that hovers on human and housing population, growth and sustainable development of the nation. Buttressing how census could be imperative for all the sectors: socio-economic, political, general security etcetera. Mohammed *et al.* (2019:16) observed that:

Over time and from pre-independence to date, several heads and housing counts have been conducted to obtain the total number of persons in Nigeria over given periods. Those were particularly important as no meaningful planning and development could be made and successfully implemented without knowing who and how many to plan for, what to plan and at what time? Without these, no sustainable development can be achieved.

As significant as census is to the socio-economic advancement, political landscape, security architecture and the jigsaw for developmental stride and other multi-circular sectors of the nation, worryingly, it has remained utopia and elusive for the Nigerian government to come up with the exact number of her citizens and the accurate statistics of housing units in the nation. Though there have been population exercises conducted in the past aimed at ascertaining the population of the country, but on each occasion, it has always ended in one controversy or the other. According to Akanni (2020), "all previous attempts at conducting population and housing censuses in Nigeria have been beset with challenges. These have ranged from staffing and logistical shortages to undue political interference and manipulation. Controversies and disputes have followed". The last in the series of censuses and controversies was the 2006 national census. Figures recorded in the exercise could not be relied upon as there were sharp practices that undermined and increased the number geometrically beyond what the country would even have been in two more decades away from the time.

Indeed, it is not unnatural that there were issues responsible for the fictitious and over-blotted figures declared at the end of the exercise. A good example is the heterogeneity of Nigerian society, as each region was careful of being dominated or marginalised from the scheme of things. Stalings (2006) argued that, “elite are often over-zealous about the value and importance of population census, and they always do anything, not only to enumerate all their people, but also engage in various illegalities: electoral violence, falsification and manipulation of population figures”. Making validation on what orchestrated the outrageous figures of censuses in Nigeria. Idike and Okechukwu (2015:47) argued that, “census politics in Nigeria is conterminous to petty-bourgeois politics. It refers to the struggle amongst states and/ or ethnic nationalities towards the inflation of census figures to their selfish advantage”. This position has further been reechoed by Serra and Jerven (2021) when they opined that anomaly accompanied census figures in Nigeria is as a result of “importance of population returns for federal parliamentary representation and the allocation of federal revenues and social services, it is not surprising that Nigerian census results have been hotly contested”.

A decade and half down the lane, the question glued on everyone’s lip is, how many are we? The unsurpassed answer to the unanswered question remains rooted in the dictum; ‘your guess is as good as mine’. Part of this quagmire stems from the fact that the nation has not been able to organise and conduct census exercise for nearly two decades running. Conversely, an eyebrow has not been further raised as to why Nigeria as a nation keeps begging and guessing for an answer whenever the question of the precise population of the country gets raised even in the 21st century. This is due to the contestable figures released in 2006 by the National Population Commission (NPC), that pegged Nigeria’s population at 140,431,790 and also the failure of successive governments to conduct credible census since 2006, has further boosted everyone’s speculation and thickened the debate as per the actual number of people in the country not leaving out the academics, researchers, content developers and policymakers off the guess desk.

Still in the doldrums of exact population becoming insatiable for the country, the Chairman of National Population Census (NPC), Nasir Kwarra maintained that, in the absence of an actual census we formally make projections, and we estimate that as of 2020, the estimated population of Nigeria is 206 million (Sahara Reporters, 2020). However, with the recent declaration by the Chairman National Population Commission (NPC), Nasir Kwarra, the nation does not seem to be in a hurry to provide an answer to the puzzle of ‘how many are we? This is evident in the speech of the NPC boss, as he categorically affirmed that as a country “we are not going to conduct census this year” (Vanguard, 2021). In the face of this lingering dilemma that has kept the argument going about census figures and the inability of a genuine census exercise which could have resulted in a much improved or a robust transformation of sectors like socio-economic, political landscape and security architecture of the nation.

Rather, the missing link has impeded development, dwarfed the socio-economic and handicapped security design of the nation. As a response to these challenges, the paper examined amongst other things how virile national census policy can translate to improved peace, security and development of the nation.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's policy and strategic mechanisms as regard exact population of the country which can readily be an operational modus when it comes to planning and implementation of societal transformational initiatives to enhance socio-economic activities, political stability, robust security network and a facelift of infrastructural development of the nation has been hampered and hindered by the continued utilization of the defective, outdated and fly-by-night census figures of 2006. As such, various government policies, strategies and programmes having direct implications on the population of the country have failed to measure up with the current realities of the day. The failures have been amplified and replicated in the critical sectors of the country. For instance, security which is the umbilical cord shaping the existence of other important sectors has not been adequately taken care of due to the inconsistency with data available for tackling challenges such as kidnapping, human trafficking, cattle rustling, banditry and other terrorism-related activities.

However, a question that must first be answered by any sane government before embarking on tactics aimed at cushioning these acts and also implementing developmental infrastructure that has to do with people is to sincerely identify the number of people inhabiting the surface of the country at a regular interval. Thus, if after more than fourteen years Nigerian government still largely depend on the festering 2006 census, which has been relied upon too long as if it has the whole country under its feet and becomes obligatory for the figures therein to be constantly used in piloting policies, programmes and implementation, then, it does appear the government has finally gave up on providing a convincing answer to the question of how many are we? Again, it is not surprising that the outcomes of the dependency on the old-fashioned 2006 census figures have not been anything different from disappointment, because those policies and initiatives have been outshined by the dwarfed socio-economic realities and gross security challenges such as incessant arm banditry, eternal Boko Haram insurgency, ceaseless farmers/herders clashes, festering cattle rustling, constant kidnapping and other issues increasingly threatening the relative peace, safety and survival of the nation.

Again, there is a clear stagnation of infrastructural development which does not imply heydays for the wellbeing of the citizenry. Following this lapse, machinery has to be set in motion at conducting census at intervals to improve the security, peace and development of the nation. Besides, every idea that seeks to transform a nation hangs and hinges on dependable census. As enshrined in the words of Harper and Mayhew (2012), that it was possible to replicate local

census enumeration and there are yet again many other data sources available to academics but national coherence can only be found in the census.

Aims of the Study

The main aim of the study is to examine how national census policy can meaningfully translate to improvement on peace, security and development of the nation. The other specific objectives are:

- i.** To determine the importance of census on the peace, security and development of the nation;
- ii.** To examine the extent of census data usage while strategically implementing the security architecture and execution of infrastructural development of the nation.

Literature Exposition

As far as census and related issues are concerned, there are arrays of literature on them. As such, most of the scholarly inquiry/papers have explicitly espoused population, housing, statistics and sustainable development. Others have discussed issues hanging around population figures, such as falsification, quota politics, problems and prospects, patterns of population distribution and administrative census as an alternative to the conventional headcount system. Writing in support of census as the elemental conceived and most reliable form of researching that others strive to emulate, Golata (2014:1) stressed that, a population census is not only the oldest research, best-known, well-formed in terms of methodology, but also a research, which is widely regarded as the most reliable data source. Equally, Mohammed *et al.* (2019: 21) argued that:

The fundamental objective of conducting a population and housing census all over the world is also to set forth plans for development that is targeted to be achieved and sustained. Statistics, figures, facts and forecasts are, therefore, made, analysed, documented, used and also followed up as working plans to attain the desired level of development.

Coming out of this exposition, the definition of census thus appeals to our attention. Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations defined a population census as the total process of planning, collecting, compiling, evaluating, disseminating and analyzing demographic, economic and social data at the smallest geographic level pertaining, at a specified time, to all persons in a country or a well-delimited part of a country (United Nations, 2017:2). Similarly, a housing census is defined as, the total process of planning, collecting, compiling, evaluating, disseminating and analysing statistical data relating to the number and condition of housing units and facilities as available to the households pertaining, at a specified time, to all living quarters and occupants thereof in a country or a well-delimited part of a country(United Nations, 2017:3).However, combining the two descriptions within the context of the census, the United Nations defined census as an operation that produces an

official count of a country's population, right down to the lowest level of geographical detail, at regular intervals (UNECE, 2006:6-7).

However, moving away from the concentration on definition of census to the strategic relevance or indispensability of census to issues of policy, socio-economic and other social aspects, in short, census end product (figures) are utilized diversely. However, the interrelationship is considered mutually dependent on census, peace, security and sustainable development of a nation. In other words, how census as an instrument could help position the security, safety and enduring development of the nation towards being a 21st century compliant nation. Census importance on a wide range of decisions and sectors that affects humanity has been described as *sin qua non* in the communiqué of the United Nations (United Nations, 2017:1), "establishing a public consensus on priorities would be almost impossible to achieve if it were not built on census counts". Therefore, it is observable that development is indispensable to planning which is rooted in robust and accurate census figures and whilst development has to do with a tactical change in security architecture, sustainable development and advancement of various human aspects needed to achieve desired progress, every country's safety and peace is determined by its development which is attached to the reliability of census module obtained in the country.

Nonetheless, the relevance of census to planning, implementation and execution of public initiatives which performance is mirrored through critical sectors such as economy, security and sustainable development of any nation has been stressed by United Nations as follows:

The population and housing census plays an essential role in public administration. The results of a census are used as a critical reference to ensure equity in the distribution of wealth, government services and representation nationwide by informing the distribution and allocation of government funds among various regions and districts for education, health services, delineating electoral districts at the national and local levels and measuring the impact of industrial development, to name a few (United Nations, 2017:1).

Expanding census relevancy to a multipurpose usage, Egeler *et al.* (2013:396) argued that, "the usability of the results has become much more varied. It ranges from policy issues and economic aspects to social themes. In the statistical field, too, census results are used in manifold ways".

Theoretical Perspective

The study adopted symbolic interactionism theory as the substratum of explanation. Symbolic interactionism is one of numerous explicative models commonly adopted in social science, humanity and related disciplines for *explanandum* of phenomena. The model was first used by Mead (1934). However, it was Blumer (1969) who refined it further to the status of a theoretical outlook. The development ensured that the theory could be used to explain varieties of

phenomena such as genesis and evolution of meaning and identity. Three central hypotheses underscore Blumer's formulation of symbolic interactionism, the assumptions are:

i. That human beings act toward things based on the meanings that things have for them.

ii. That the meaning of such things is derived from, and arises out of, the social interaction that one has with one's fellows.

iii. That these meanings are handled in, and modified through, an interpretive process used by the person in dealing with the things he encounters.

Symbolic interactionism has further been given a facelift by scholars such as Maines (1977) and Stryker (1981) by dynamism, symbolic interactionism has, in consequence, progressed rapidly and its applicability stretched to the school of thought like social science, humanity and management sciences. It is vital to know that symbolic interactionism is not only about the study of symbols. The phrase 'symbolic' points to a central idea that humans exist in a world of objects that do not have built-in connotations. As a substitute, the denotations of objects occur out of the connotations that people allot to them in the course of daily group exchanges amid others. Through these dealings, mutual as well as local connotations surface but are always theme to the likelihood of transformation. This ongoing progression of analysis takes place chiefly employing the common symbols of language. People make sense of their world using symbols that convey the meanings of different objects, and these meanings (including the concept of self) in turn influence people's actions toward the objects (Swan and Bowers, 1998). Population and housing censuses are conducted to obtain information, data and statistics required for planning and development across the board.

Methodology

The cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Ekiti state in the South-Western part of Nigeria. Three towns (Ado, Ikere and Ikole) were purposely selected as representing the three senatorial districts of the state. The choice of the towns was carefully made because they are the biggest town in each senatorial district of the state. Ekiti state was among the six states created by the former military head of state, Late General Sanni Abacha, on the 1st of October, 1996. The state was formerly part of the old Ondo state before the bifurcation in 1996. The state is endowed with human resources coupled with agricultural supportive vegetation which invariably makes its bulk population preoccupied with farming. The populations for the study were made up of farmers, civil servants, politicians and youths from, 18 years and above. The study used quota random sampling method to select respondents across different cadres. The study employed a blend of quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. Data analyses were done using a simple percentage and frequency distribution table, while the qualitative data was

analysed through content analysis and verbatim quotations by the research participants which added value and aphorism to the study.

Result, Findings and Discussion

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Gender		
Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages (%)
Males	182	67.4
Females	88	32.6
Total	270	100
Age Distribution		
Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages (%)
18 – 40	185	68.5
41 – 60	57	21.1
60 and above years	28	10.4
Total	270	100
Education Qualifications		
Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages (%)
Trade & Vocational Training	29	10.7
Primary	20	7.4
Secondary	65	24.1
Tertiary	156	57.8
Total	270	100
Employment Status		
Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages (%)
Student	71	26.3
Unemployed	118	43.7
Employed	53	19.6
Retired	28	10.4
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The demographic characteristics of respondents are represented in Table 1 above. The gender distribution indicated that 182 deciphering 67.4 percent of

respondents were males, while 88 representing 32.6 percent were females. The indication of this is that the bulk of respondents were dominated by males with 67.4%.

The respondents' age distribution showed that 185 equaling 68.5 percent were between the ages of 18-40, 57 representing 21.1 percent were within the age range of 41-60, while 28 translating 10.4 percent were 60 years and above. The import of this analysis is that majority of the respondents 68.5% fall within the age group of 18-40 years of age.

The respondents' educational qualifications show that 29 implying 10.7 percent have a trade and vocational training certificate, 20 representing 7.4 percent of the respondents possess a primary school leaving certificate, and 65 equaling 24.1 percent of the respondents have secondary education, while 156 deciphering 57.8 percent have tertiary education. The translation of this is that the majority (57.8%) of the respondents attained tertiary education.

The respondents' employment status shows that 71 deciphering 26.3 percent were students, 118 indicating 43.7 percent were unemployed, and 53 implying 19.6 percent of the respondents are employed, while 28 representing 10.4 percent of the respondents are retirees. This means that majority of the respondents with 43.7% are unemployed.

Objective 1: To Determine the Importance of Census on the Peace, Security and Development of the Nation

Table 2: Intensity of Census as Template for Robust Peace, Security and Development of the Nation

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages (%)
Very large importance	77	28.5
Large importance	125	46.3
Little importance	49	18.2
No importance	19	7.0
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 2 indicates that 77 of the respondents translating 28.5 percent observed that census has very large importance in ensuring robust peace, security and development of the nation, 125 of the respondents representing 46.3 were of the thought that peace, security and development of the nation rest largely on census template and 49 of the respondents translating 18.2 percent think census has little importance on the robust peace, security and development of the nation, however, 19 of the respondents signifying 7.0 percent believed that census has no importance on robust peace, security and development of the nation. On the importance of census, here is a respondent's reaction:

Census is important not only to security but to all the sectors in the country. Can you identify a sector that does not need an accurate census blueprint for planning? If your answer to

my question is unenthusiastic, then, it is a required catalyst for advancement and an econometric measurement of equitable distribution of infrastructure across board. It is when this is done we can have a meaningful and unbridled development we all clamour for in this 21st century. IDI/M/Lanyer/ 2021.

Table 3: Failure of Credible Census has Handicapped Peace, Security and Development of the Nation

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages %
Very large impairment	131	48.5
Large impairment	92	34.1
Little impairment	33	12.2
No impairment	14	5.2
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 3 shows that 131 of the respondents representing 48.5 percent noted that failure of the credible census has done a very large impairment to the peace, security and development of the nation, 92 of the respondents translating 34.1 percent held the view that failure of the credible census has done large impairment to the peace, security and development of the nation, and 33 of the respondents indicating 12.2 percent opined that failure of the credible census has done little impairment to the peace, security and development of the nation, while 14 of the respondents deciphering 5.2 percent observed that the failure of the credible census has not done any impairment to the peace, security and development of the nation. A respondent quips does:

In my point of view, most of the problems manifesting in abridged peace and insecurity which have not been abated despite the responses from the security agencies, have been as a result of the inadequate personnel trailing the unknown population. In other words, if we can have genuine census of the country, at least government would know that there is a need for the ratio of security personnel to be commensurate with that of the nation's population. IDI/M/Civil Servant/ 2021.

Table 4: Periodic Census Exercise is a Yardstick Needed for Continued Improvement in Peace, Security and Development of the Nation

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages %
Very large requirement	88	32.6
Large requirement	152	56.3
Little requirement	24	8.9
No requirement	6	2.2
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4 indicates that 88 of the respondents representing 32.6 percent held the view that for continuous improvement in peace, security and development of the nation, periodic census exercise is a very large requirement, 152 of the respondents deciphering 56.3 percent said periodic census exercise is a large requirement for continuous improvement in peace, security and development of the nation and 24 of the respondents equaling 8.9 percent observed that periodic census exercise is of little requirement in terms of yardstick for the continuous improvement of peace, security and development of the nation, while 6 of the respondents indicating 2.2 percent upheld the view that periodic census exercise is of no requirement as a yardstick for the continuous improvement of peace, security and development of the nation.

Objective 2: To Examine the Extent of Census Data Usage while Strategically Implementing the Security Architecture and Execution of Infrastructural Development of the Nation

Table 5: Government Apply Census Data while Preparing the Annual Budget of Security Sector and Infrastructural Development of the Nation

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages %
Very large consideration	17	6.3
Large consideration	41	15.2
Little consideration	130	48.1
No consideration	82	30.4
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 5 illustrates that 17 of the respondents translating 6.3 percent noted that a very large consideration is given to census data by the government while preparing the annual budget of the security sector and infrastructural development of the nation, 41 of the respondents representing 15.2 percent observed that a large consideration is given to census data by the government while preparing the annual budget of the security sector and infrastructural development of the nation and 130 of the respondents indicating 48.1 percent held the opinion that in preparation of annual budget of the security sector and infrastructural development of the nation, census data is given little consideration by the government, while 82 of the respondents equaling 30.4 held the view that no consideration is given to census data by the government while preparing the annual budget of the security sector and infrastructural development of the nation.

Ordinarily, this should form the major consideration while preparing the nation's annual budget. But the 'holocausts' we have in the corridor of power are majorly preoccupied with how much will enter their pockets rather than what stands to benefit the nation as a whole. That is to tell you that these issues are never put on the front burner while preparing the annual budget. IDI/M/ Civil Servant/ 2021.

Table 6: What Extent do the Nation's Security and Developmental Policies Depend on Census Data

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages %
Very large extent	26	9.6
Large extent	63	23.3
Little extent	122	45.2
No extent	59	21.9
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 6 illustrates that 26 of the respondents deciphering 9.6 percent believed that to a very large extent the nation's security and developmental policies depend on census data, 63 of the respondents translating 23.3 percent said to a large extent, the nation's security and developmental policies depend on census data and 122 of the respondents deciphering 45.2 percent believed that to a little extent, the nation's security and developmental policies depend on census data, while 59 of the respondents equaling 21.9 percent believed that the nation's security and developmental policies do not depend on census data. On policymakers using census data in formulating policies, one respondent has this to say:

Most of these policies are done haphazardly and therefore fail to have a positive impact on citizens. Ours have been somewhat of building a castle in the air. The policies are never tailored towards addressing any issue because there has never been consideration given to the actual number of people, and it is less surprising because people's welfare has never been a topmost priority for policymakers. IDI/F/ Student/ 2021.

Table 7: The Security Agencies Use Census Data in Carrying out Geo-surveillance in the Country

Variables	Frequency (n=270)	Percentages %
Very large degree	11	4.0
Large degree	24	8.9
Little degree	140	51.9
No degree	95	35.2
Total	270	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 7 signifies that 11 of the respondents translating 4.0 percent noted that very large degree, the security agencies use census data in carrying out geo-surveillance in the country, 24 of the respondents deciphering 8.9 percent believed that to a large degree, the security agencies use census data in carrying out geo-surveillance in the country and 140 of the respondents indicating 51.9 percent noted that census data is of little degree for security agencies in carrying out geo-surveillance in the country, while 95 of the respondents representing 35.2 percent held the view that census data is of no degree for security agencies in carrying out geo-surveillance in the country.

Limitation of the Study and Suggestion for Further Study

Since the sample size of the study represented only a portion and sparse of the people in three communities in Ekiti State, the generalization of the study must be made with precise tenderness. It is advised that future studies in this spot should cover other communities within and outside the state to accommodate views and opinions from other parts of the country which is tantamount to fairness, representation of geographical spread and ample generalization.

Conclusion

The conclusion arrived in this study is that the continued underprivileged developmental returns, fragile peace and vain security architecture of the country have been further boosted by the abysmal national census policy of the country. In other words, there have been lackadaisical attitudes on the part of successive governments towards fine-tuning a credible and reliable census for the nation. This shunning of responsibility or inability is responsible for the gap since the last census exercise which is closing on the double of the standard period advocated by the United Nations, which is ten years interval. Nonconformity with this standard, one could not eschew the fact that the country has waited too long for another census exercise to happen. Finally, its failure has done more of retrogression than improvement to the multi-circular sectors of the system. Hence, national census policy remains a benchmark or catalyst that must be fulfilled for the peace, security and development of the nation.

Recommendations

Stemming from the opinions expressed by respondents in this research, the following are drawn and weighed as avid recommendations:

1. Census exercise, having experienced doldrums and moratoriums for too long, it has become an emergency issue that seeks emergency response from the government to organize another round of population and housing census exercise liberally done with genuine resolve to ascertaining the exact number of people and housing units in the country. Doing this will no doubt put a stoppage to the speculations enveloping the actual population of the country and also help a great deal in planning and implementing policies in the country.

2. The Nigerian government must imbibe and practice the minimum standard of period in conducting census exercise as advocated by the United Nations, which is a decennial (10 years period) population and housing census that is crucial and central to the evolvement and optimal performance of Nigeria's socio-economic, political, security, peace and sustainable development of the country. The emphasis is that both the population and housing units are ever-changing variables, hence, there has to be periodic census hounding to accommodate updates and changes.

3. However, it is important to correct the impression that census is done for number sake or a jamboree exercise. Rather, it is done with the intent desire to have positive reflections when applied in strengthening the socio-economic, political landscape, security architecture, proper infrastructural development that cut across the divide and other sectors that are vital for people's welfare and wellbeing and also upward evolution of the country.

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